

**New subspecies of *Dorcadion scabricolle* (Dalman, 1817) of
Iran and Azerbaijan
(Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)**

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Key words: Coleoptera, Cerambycidae, Dorcadionini, *Dorcadion*, taxonomy, new subspecies.

Summary: Three new subspecies *Dorcadion* (*Cribridorcadion*) *scabricolle* *skoupyi*, **ssp. n.** *D. (C.) s. gilanense*, **ssp. n.** and *D. (C.) s. sagezense*, **ssp. n.** are described from Iran. *D. (C.) s. subcorpulentum* Breuning, 1946, **new rank.** is downgraded from a species.

INTRODUCTION

Several series of *D. scabricolle* collected recently in Iran by Czech Republic colleagues allowed me to begin the study of the taxonomy diversity of Iranian populations.

Several abbreviations used in the text:

MD - collection of M. Danilevsky, Moscow (Russia)

ML - collection of M. Lazarev, Moscow (Russia)

VS - collection of V. Skoupy, Kamenné Žehrovice (Czech Republic)

ZIN - Zoological Institute of Russian Academy of Sciences, Sankt-Petersburg (Russia)

ZMM - Zoological Museum of Moscow State University, Moscow (Russia)

***Dorcadion* (*Cribridorcadion*) *scabricolle* (Dalman, 1817)**

(Figs 1-16; Map: 1-11)

Lamia (*Dorcadion*) *scabricolle* Dalman, 1817: 174 - "Habitat in Georgia".

Dorcadion corpulentum Ménétériés, 1832: 226 - "Lenkoran".

Dorcadion scabricolle, Ménétériés, 1832: 226 - "Lenkoran"; Falderman, 1837: 279; Kraatz, 1873: 50 - "Caucasus, Georgien, Persien"; Ganglbauer, 1884: 490 - "Caucasus, Persien"; Plavilstshikov, 1948: 131, 148 - Armenia, Transcaucasia, West Asia; Fuchs & Breuning, 1971: 437 - "Yozgat"; Demelt, 1963: 146 - "Akshehir"; Abai, 1969: 52 - "Azerbaijan: Tabriz, Ardabil, Moghan"; Braun, 1978: 104 - several locality Turkey and Iran;

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- Miroshnikov, 2004: 136 - "Caucasus, Grozny, Vostrikov"; Özdikmen, 2006: 82 - "Ankara: Kizilcahamam, Yukari Canli; Ankara: Kizilcahamam, Salin village; Ankara: Kizilcahamam, Yenimahalle village; Ankara: Ayaş road, Başayaş village env., Ayaş Beli"; 2007: 307 - "Caucasus, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Iran"; Özdikmen, Turgut & Güzel, 2009: 86 - "Ankara: Ayaş; Kizilcahamam, Işık Dağı"; Özdikmen, 2011: 65 - Western and Eastern Mediterranean; 2012: 79.
- Dorcadion modestum* Tournier, 1872: 338.
- Dorcadion scabricolle* var. D ("Dorc. lutescens Kraatz"), 1873: 50.
- Dorcadion scabricolle sevangense* Reitter, 1889: 41 - "Gotschka- oder Sevangesees im nördlichen, russischen Armenien", Daniilevsky, 1999: 25; 2010: 252.
- Dorcadion scabricolle caramanicum* K. Daniel & J. Daniel, 1903: 332 - Cilicischer Taurus; Danilevsky, 2010: 252.
- Dorcadion scabricolle elisabetholicum* Suvorov, 1915: 119 - Elisabethpol environs [now Gindzha].
- Dorcadion (Compsodorcadion) scabricolle*, Plavilstchikov, 1932: 193 - "Transcaucasia".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scabricolle* m. *aeruginosum* Breuning, 1946: 121 - "Ak-Cheir, Anatolie"; 1958: 30.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scabricolle* m. *basalireductum* Breuning, 1946: 121 - "Suvant, Caucase"; 1958: 30.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scabricolle* m. *latefasciatum* Breuning, 1946: 121 - "Erivan, Transcaucasie".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scabricolle* m. *bulghardaghense* Breuning, 1946: 121 - "Bulghar-Maaden, Anatolie"; 1958: 30.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scabricolle* m. *nubilosum* Breuning, 1946: 121 - "Erivan, Transcaucasie"; 1958: 30.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) subcorpulentum* Breuning, 1946: 121 - "Choi, Perse".
- Dorcadion scabricolle* var. *micheli* Pic, 1948: 13 - "Aresch".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scabricolle* m. *albithorax* Breuning, 1956: 724 - "environs d'Ankara"; 1958: 30.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scabricolle* m. *postceinteruptum* Breuning, 1956: 724 - "environs d'Erivan"; 1958: 30.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scabricolle* m. *sevangense*, Breuning, 1958: 30.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scabricolle* m. *caramanicum*, Breuning, 1958: 30.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scabricolle* m. *modestum*, Breuning, 1958: 30.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scabricolle* m. *corpulentum*, Breuning, 1958: 30; 1962: 458, part. (= *micheli* Pic, 1948).
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scabricolle* m. *elisabetholicum* Breuning, 1958: 30.
- Dorcadion scabricolle* m. *corpulentum* ab. *supermodestum* Plavilstchikov, 1958: 218.
- Dorcadion scabricolle* m. *latefasciatum*, Breuning, 1958: 30; Abai, 1969: 52 - "Azarбайдjan: Azarschahr".
- Dorcadion (Autodorcadion) scabricolle*, Plavilstchikov, 1958: 215.
- Dorcadion scabricolle* m. *scabricolle* ab. *solitaneum* Plavilstchikov, 1958: 217.

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- Dorcadion scabricolle* m. *masculochromum* Plavilstchikov, 1958: 217.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scabricolle*, Breuning, 1958: 30 - "Perse, Transcaucasie, Anatolie"; 1962: 456 - "Von Persim: Mts. Elbrus über Transkaukasien und Armenien bis Anatolien, ca. die Umgebung von Ankara, der Sultan Dagh und der Bulghar Dagh verbreitet"; Sama G., Rapuzzi P. & Özdikmen H., 2012: 35 - "Sivas: 20 km east of the crossroad to Zara; Beypinari; Tunceli: 15 km north of Pülümür".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scabricolle paphlagonicum* Breuning, 1962: 459 - "Anatolien: Kastamuni"; Danilevsky, 2010: 252.
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scabricolle* m. *subbasalireductum* Breuning, 1962: 459 - "Anatolien: Kastamuni".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scabricolle* m. *humeralibivittatum* Breuning, 1962: 459 - "Anatolien: Kastamuni".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scabricolle balikesirensense* Breuning, 1962: 460 - "Anatolien: Balikesir"; Danilevsky, 2010: 252.
- Pedestredorcadion scabricolle*, Villiers, 1967: 365 - "Iran: Tabriz; Kiklik-Dagh; Mazanderan, Ghilan, Talysh; Lurestan et de Zendjan à Ardebil".
- Pedestredorcadion subcorpulentum*, Villiers, 1967: 365 - "Iran: Choi".
- Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scabricolle uludaghicum* Breuning, 1970: 98 - "Turquie: l'Ulu Dagh près de Brousse".
- Dorcadion scabricolle corpulentum*, Abai, 1969: 53 - "Azarбайдjan: Thabriz"; Fuchs & Breuning, 1971: 437 - "Van zu. Oezalp".
- Dorcadion scabricolle paphlagonicum*, Fuchs & Breuning, 1971: 437 - "Kusonkiran".
- Dorcadion scabricolle nakhiczewanum* Danilevsky, 1999: 28 - "Azerбайдzhan Republic, Nakhichevan, south slope of Bichenek pass (Batabad)"; 2010: 252.
- Dorcadion scabricolle paiz* Danilevsky, 1999: 28 - "Azerбайдzhan, Nakhichevan, Paiz"; 2010: 252.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scabricolle scabricolle*, Danilevsky, 1999: 25 - Armenia (Arai-Ler Mt., Ashotzk, Biurakan, Gami, Gehard, Dzhrarat, Dzhrvezh, Khosrov, Marmashen, Megri, Nubarashen, Tzahkadzor, Tzovagiuh), Azerбайдzhan (Khanlar, Gasmalian, Mistan) and in Nakhichevan part (Bichenek, Buzgov, Negram), allover Turkey and in North Iran; 2010: 252; Özdikmen, 2010: 1149, 1160 - "Kharamanmaraş prov.: Afşin, Emirilyas village, Mağaraözü district"; Özdikmen, 2012: 79.
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scabricolle*, Özdikmen, Güven & Gören, 2010: 1149, 1160 - "Kharamanmaraş prov.: Afşin, Emirilyas village, Mağaraözü district"; Sakenin et al., 2011: 10 "Iran: West Azarbayjan province: Salmas".
- Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scabricolle crassofasciatum* Özdikmen, 2013: 56 - "Turkey: Anatolia: Balikesir prov.: Edremit, Sankiz hill, 39°42'N 26°49'E".

Type locality. Georgia – according to the original description.

Diagnosis. Head usually glabrous, or pubescent in autochromal

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females; antennae thick, reaching apical elytral forth (males) or elytral middle (females), black with red 1st joint or sometimes totally black; prothorax transverse with wide rounded lateral tubercles; pronotum usually glabrous and shining, with very rough more or less dense punctation (sometimes lusterless with very dense punctation), or pubescent and less roughly punctuated in autochromal females; elytra regularly oval with very dense regular pubescence, usually mostly black in males and androchromal females, very rare about totally white in certain subspecies or partly brownish in androchromal females; short semierect elytral setae indistinct, or hardly visible in females; males always without dorsal elytral stripes, often small basal rudiments present on form of white spots; only autochromal females often with wide irregular partly interrupted dorsal pale stripes; humeral and sutural stripes always well developed, narrow or wide, often with irregular internal margins, sometimes widened to about whole elytral surface, making elytra totally white; humeral white elytral stripes never accompanied with velvety black lines; elytral carinae usually absent or slightly pronounced; legs are usually totally red, but sometimes more or less darkened, with dense pale pubescence; femora and tibiae densely punctated; abdomen with dense recumbent white pubescence, finely punctated; last abdominal tergites widely rounded, sternites finely emarginated; body length in males: 10,9-16,3 mm, width: 3,9-5,2 mm; body length in females: 12,1-18,4 mm, width: 5,1-7,2 mm.

Distribution. About whole Transcaucasia (Georgia, Armenia, Azerbaijan), North Iran, Turkey.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scabricolle scabricolle* (Dalman, 1817)**

(Figs 15-16)

Lamia (Dorcadion) scabricolle Dalman, 1817: 174 - "Habitat in Georgia".

Type locality. Georgia - according to the original description.

Diagnosis. Pronotum in males and in androchromal females with very dense punctation, nearly lusterless, male elytra with very narrow regular sutural and humeral stripes; body length in males: 10,9-16,3 mm, width: 3,9-5,2 mm; body length in females: 12,1-18,4 mm, width: 5,1-7,2 mm.

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Distribution. Georgia (figs 15-16) only specimens from near Mtskheta available; Armenia, known localities are: Aragyukh (40°24'41.24''N 44°31'47.88''E), Arai-Ler Mt., Ashotsk, Byurakan, Garni, Gehard, Dzhrarat, Dzhrapi (40°33'1.88''N 43°41'36.66''E), Dzhrvezh, Erivan, Haizavan, 3 km SE Ishkhanasar (39°33'2.03''N 46°4'27.22''E), Khosrov, Makenis, Marmashen, Megri, Novoseltsevo (41°04'01.66''N 44°17'24.82''E), Nubarashen, Sevan Lake, 2 km E Sisian Pass (39°40'30''N 45°45'E), 4 km NW Tekh (39°34'6.97''N 46°25'46.64''E), Tsahkadzor, Tsovagyukh; Azerbaijan (Ganja formerly Elisavetpol), Khanlar, three localities are known in Nakhichevan area (Bichenek, Buzgov, Gemur, Negram); several populations in North Iran and Turkey.

Materials. 2 males, 2 females, Georgia, Mtskheta, 07.04.2010 - MD; big series from different localities of Armenia, Azerbaijan, Nakhichevan and Turkey - ZIN, ZMM, MD, ML.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scabricolle skoupyi ssp.n.

(Figs 1-4; Map: 1-2)

Pedestredorcadion scabricolle, Villiers, 1967: 365 part. - "Iran: Tabriz; Kiklik-Dagh; Mazanderan, Ghilan, Talysh; Lurestan et de Zendjan à Ardebil".

Type locality. Iran: Ardabil pr., E of Khalkhal.

Diagnosis. Antennae black, with dark-red 1st joint; vertex roughly punctated; pronotum in males shining with scattered big dots; elytral stripes in males relatively wide, humeral stripes widened posteriorly with irregular margin; sutural stripe often about two times narrower than humeral; basal rudiments of dorsal stripes usually absent, but sometimes present; legs totally dark-red; females androchromal or autochromal, ground elytral pubescence black or brown, poorly developed pale dorsal elytral stripe if present, then irregular and never complete; humeral and sutural stripes rather wide and irregular; body length in males: 13.2-16.4 mm, width: 4.6-5.7 mm; body length in females: 14.4-17.8 mm, width: 5.5-6.9 mm.

Distribution. Iran: Ardabil pr., E of Khalkhal, 2100 m; road to pass Khalkhal / Asalem, 2068 m. (37°35' N, 48°38'E); 20 km NW Kiwi; 10 km N Khalkhal, Ali-abad.

Material. Holotype, 1 male, "Iran, Ardabil pr., E of Khalkhal, 2100 m., 26.05.2010, Skoupy leg." - ML; 88 Paratypes: 42 males, 8 females, Iran,

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Ardabil pr., E of Khalkhal, 2100 m., 26.05.2010, Skoupý - VS, ML, Michálik: Hlinik nad Hronom (Slovakia); 25 males, 2 females, Iran, Ardabil pr., Khalkhal, 2068 m., 37°35' N, 48°38'E, 26.05.2010, Zd. Košťál – VS, ML; 3 males, 3 females, Iran, Ardabil pr., road to pass Khalkhal / Asalem, 2068 m., 37°35' N, 48°38'E, 26.05.2010, Michálik - VS; 1 male, 1 female, IR (Azarbaijan), 20 km NW Kiwi, 2000 m, (loc.-Hashtian), 14.04.1996, W.Heinz - MD; 1 male, 2 females, IR Azerb., 10 km N Khalkhal, Ali-abad, 1500 m, 14.04.1996, W.Heinz - MD.

Etymology. The new subspecies is dedicated to Vladimír Skoupý (Czech Republic), who collected the most part of the type series.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scabricolle gilanense ssp.n.

(Figs 5-6; Map: 3-4)

Type locality. Iran: Gilan, Umg. Kharpu.

Diagnosis. Antennae black with red 1st joint; vertex moderately roughly punctated; pronotum in males shining, with scattered medium-sized dots, which are never conjugated; elytral stripes in males narrow, humeral stripe about as wide as sutural or wider; basal rudiments of dorsal stripes absent; legs totally red; females only androchromal, pronotal dots small and can be rather dense; body length in males: 14.0-15.4 mm, width: 4,8-5.7 mm; body length in females: 14.4-15.2 mm, width: 5.6-6.1 mm.

Distribution. Iran: Gilan, Umg. Kharpu; Deylaman E of Rudbar.

Material. Holotype, 1 male, “IR Gilan, Umg. Kharpu, 2000 m., 12.IV.1996, Heinz leg.” - MD; 7 Paratypes: 1 female, IR (Gilan), Kharpu, 2000 m, 12.04.1996, W.Heinz - MD; 2 males, 1 female, Iran, Gilan, Umg. Kharpu, 2000 m. 12.04.1996, Heinz - VS, ML; 2 males, 1 female, Iran, Gilan, Deylaman E of Rudbar, 13.06.2009, Heinz - VS.

Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scabricolle sagezense ssp.n.

(Figs7-8; Map: 5-6)

Type locality. Iran: Kordestan, 6 km N Sagez,

Diagnosis. Vertex moderately punctated; pronotum in males with very dense, relatively small, partly conjugated punctation; elytral stripes in males regular, very narrow, about equal in width; very distinct basal rudiments of dorsal stripes always present; females only autochromal; ground elytral pubescence brown or pale brown;

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elytral carinae better pronounced; humeral stripes about two times wider than sutural; body length in males: 13.2-16.4 mm, width: 4.6-5.7 mm; body length in females: 15.4-17.8 mm, width: 6.0-6.9 mm.

Distribution. Iran: 6 km N Sagez; 60 km NE of Takab.

Material. Holotype, 1 male, "Ir (Kordestan), 1500 m, 6 km n. Sagez, 24.III.1996, Heinz leg." - ML; 5 Paratypes: 1 male, 2 females, Iran, Kordestan, 6 km N Sagez, 1500 m, 24.03.1996, W.Heinz - VS, ML; 2 males, Iran pr., Azerbaijan, 60 km NE of Takab, 04.06.2010, Scoypý - VS.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scabricolle subcorpulentum* Breuning,
1946, new rank
(Figs 9-12; Map: 7-9)**

Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) subcorpulentum Breuning, 1946: 121 - "Choi, Perse."; 1962: 460.

Pedestredorcadion subcorpulentum Villiers, 1967: 365 - "Iran: Choi"

Pedestredorcadion scabricolle, Villiers, 1967: 365, part. - "Iran: Tabriz, Kiklik-Dagh; Mazanderan, Ghilan, Talysh; Lurestan et de Zendjan à Ardebil"

Type locality. Iran: Khoy.

Diagnosis. Antennae totally black; legs also very dark; vertex finally punctated; pronotum in males regularly punctated with relatively small dots; elytral stripes in males regular, sutural stripe about two times wider than humeral; very distinct basal rudiments of dorsal stripes present; females androchromal or autochromal with dark-brown ground pubescence; humeral elytral stripes about two times wider than sustural; body length in males: 14.5-16.5 mm, width: 5.7-5.9 mm; body length in females: 13.5-14.1 mm, width: 5.3-6.3 mm.

Distribution. Iran: 25 km SW Khoy; 15 km SE Salmas (Shahpur), (loc.-Hashtian); Paß s. Gushchi (n.Urmia)

Material. 1 male, IR Azarbaijan, 25 km SW Khoy, 1500 m, 17.04.1996, Heinz - MD; 1 male, 1 female, IR (Azarbaijan), Paß s. Gushchi (n.Urmia), 1700 m, 17.04.1996, W.Heinz - MD; 4 females, IR (Azarbaijan), 15 km SE Salmas (Shahpur), 1300 m, (loc.-Hashtian) 17.04.1996, W.Heinz - MD, ML.

Remark. *D. subcorpulentum* was described on the base of a single female similar to *D. scabricolle*. Three series of specimens close to its type locality show its real nature conspecific to *D. scabricolle* with a few but constant peculiar characters.

***Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scabricolle corpulentum* Ménériés, 1832**
(Figs 13-14; Map: 10-11)

- Dorcadion corpulentum* Ménériés, 1832: 226 - "Lenkoran"
Dorcadion scabricolle, Ménériés, 1832: 226 - "Lenkoran"; Plavilstshikov, 1948, part.: 131, 148 - Armenia, Transcaucasia, West Asia; Abai, 1969, part.: 52 - "Azerbaidjan: Tabriz, Ardabil, Moghan"; Özdikmen, 2007, part.: 307 - "Caucasus, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Iran".
Dorcadion scabricolle m. *basalireductum* Breuning, 1946: 121 - "Suvant, Caucase"; 1958: 30.
Dorcadion (Pedestredorcadion) scabricolle m. *corpulentum*, Breuning, 1958: 30; 1962: 458, part. (= *micheli* Pic, 1948).
Pedestredorcadion scabricolle, Villiers, 1967: 365, part. - "Iran: Tabriz; Kiklik-Dagh; Mazanderan, Ghilan, Talysh; Lurestan et de Zendjan à Ardebil"
Dorcadion scabricolle corpulentum, Abai, 1969: 53, part. - "Azarbidjan: Thabriz"; Fuchs & Breuning, 1971: 437, part. - "Van zu. Oezalp"
Dorcadion (Cribridorcadion) scabricolle scabricolle, Daniilevsky, 1999, part.: 25 - Armenia (Arai-Ler Mt., Ashotzk, Biurakan, Gami, Gehard, Dzhrarat, Dzhrvezh, Khosrov, Marmashen, Megri, Nubarashen, Tzahkadzor, Tzovagiuh), Azerbaidzhan (Khanlar, Gasmalian, Mistan) and in Nakhichevan part (Bichenek, Buzgov, Negram), allover Turkey and in North Iran.

Type locality. Talysh, Zuvand - according to the location of typical population in Lenkoran District.

Diagnosis. Antennae usually totally black; vertex with fine punctation, pronotum in males shining, with moderately rough very dense punctation, with partly conjugated dots; sutural and humeral elytral stripes narrow with regular margins, sutural stripe about 1.5 times wider than humeral stripe; basal rudiments of dorsal stripes distinct; femora nearly black, tibiae rather darkened; females androchromal or autochromal, ground elytral pubescence black or brown, poorly developed pale dorsal elytral stripe if present, then irregular and never complete; elytral carinae hardly visible; body length in males: 13.5-16.8 mm, width: 4.6-5.4 mm; body length in females: 12.5-18.0 mm, width: 5.2-6.6 mm.

Distribution. Azerbaijan: Talysh, Zuvand, Gasmalyan, Lerik, Bilyasar.

Material. 1 female, Zuvand, Lerik, 02.05.1974, V.Murzin - MD; 15 males, 13 females, Gasmalyan, 31.05.1979, 01-02.06.1979, 04.06.1979, 19-20.04.1980, 27.04.1984, 28.05.1987, M.Daniilevsky - MD, ML; 8 males, 6 females, Talysh, Gasmalyan, 27.04.1984, I.Belousov - MD; 10 males, 2

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females, Talysh, Gasmalyan, 10-23.05.1987, 26.05.1987, A.Dantchenko - MD; 39 males, 16 females, Talysh, Zuvand, 21.04-09.05.1988, A.Chuvilin - MD; 3 males, 2 females, Bilyasar, 16.05.1987, I.Belousov - MD.

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Figs 1-4. *D. (C.) s. spoupyi*, **ssp.n.:** 1 HT (male), 3-4 PT (female) - Iran, Ardabil pr., E of Khalkhal, 2100 m., 26.05.2010, V.Skoupý; 2 - Paratype, female, Iran, Ardabil pr., E of Khalkhal, 2068 m., 26.05.2010, 37°35' N, 48°38'E, 26.05.2010, Zd.Košťál; **Figs 5-6.** *D. (C.) s. gilanense*, **ssp.n.:** 5 - Holotype, male, Iran, Gilan, Umg. Kharpu, 2000 m., 12.04.1996, W.Heinz; 6 - Paratype, female, Iran, Gilan, Deylaman E of Rudbar, 13.06.2009, W.Heinz; **Figs 7-8.** *D. (C.) s. sagezense*, **ssp.n.:** 7 HT (male), 8 PT (female) - Iran (Kordestan), 6 km n. Sagez, 1500 m, 24.03.1996, W.Heinz; **Figs 9-12.** *D. (C.) s. subcorpulentum* Breuning, 1946, **new rank:** 9 - male, Iran, Gushchi (n.Urmia), 1700 m, 17.04.1996, W.Heinz; 10-12 - female, Iran, 15 km SE Salmas (Shahpur), 1300 m, loc.-Hashtian, 17.04.1996, W.Heinz.

Figs 13-14. *D. (C.) s. corpulentum* Ménériés, 1832: 13 (male), 14 (female) - Azerbaijan, Talysh, Zuvand, 21.04-09.05.1988, A.Chuvilin; **Figs 15-16.** *D. (C.) s. scabricolle* (Dalman, 1817): 15 (male), 16 (female) - Georgia, Mtskheta, 07.04.2010.

1-2. *D. (C.) s. skoupyi*, **ssp.n.:** 1 - Ardabil pr., E of Khalkhal; 2 - 20 km NW Kiwi;
3-4. *D. (C.) s. gilanense*, **ssp.n.:** 3 - Gilan, Umg. Kharpu; 4 - Gilan, Deylaman E of Rudbar;
5-6. *D. (C.) s. sagezense*, **ssp.n.:** 5 - 6 km N Sagez; 6 - 60 km NE of Takab;
7-9. *D. (C.) s. subcorpulentum* Breuning, 1946, **new rank:** 7 - Paß s. Gushchi (n.Urmia), 8 - 15 km SE Salmas (Shahpur), 9 - 25 km SW Khoy;
10-11. *D. (C.) s. corpulentum* Ménériés, 1832: (Azerbaijan) 10 - Gasmalyan 11 - Bilyasar.

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